

Nomenclatural novelties in Cucurbitaceae (Sicyoeae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

E-mail: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

Article Details: Received: 2025-06-07 | Accepted: 2025-06-17 | Available online: 2025-06-18

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: New names *Sicyos brandegeana* R.Kr.Singh and *S. sangeetae* R.Kr.Singh are proposed here for *Pterosicyos laciniatus* Brandegee and *Parasicyos dieterleae* Lira & R.Torres, respectively.

Keywords: Guatemala, Mexico, *Parasicyos dieterleae*, *Pterosicyos laciniatus*, *Sechiopsis laciniata*, *Sicyos*

Introduction

The genus *Sicyos* L. (family Cucurbitaceae, tribe Sicyoeae) comprises 75 species (Schaefer & Renner, 2011; Sebastian et al., 2012; Telford et al., 2012; POWO, 2025; Singh, 2025), native of Australia, New Zealand and the New World, and introduced in many parts of the Old World (POWO, 2025). Recent molecular phylogenetic studies have incorporated *Parasicyos* Dieterle, *Pterosicyos* Brandegee and *Sechiopsis* Naudin within the genus *Sicyos* (Schaefer & Renner, 2011; Sebastian et al., 2012; Telford et al., 2012). Singh (2025) proposed new combinations for *Parasicyos dieterleae* Lira & R.Torres (Acta Bot. Mex. 16: 98. 1991) and *Pterosicyos laciniatus* Brandegee (Univ. Calif. Publ. Bot. 6: 72. 1914) under the genus *Sicyos* as *S. dieterleae* (Lira & R.Torres) R.Kr.Singh and *S. laciniatus* (Brandegee) R.Kr.Singh, respectively. However, both names are illegitimate under Article 53.1 in Turland et al. (2018) as they are later homonyms of *S. dieterleae* Rodr.-Arév. & Lira (Acta Bot. Mex. 48: 15. 1999) and *S. laciniatus* L. (Sp. Pl. 2: 1013. 1753), respectively. Therefore, new names are proposed here for both taxa.

Nomenclature

Sicyos brandegeana R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Pterosicyos laciniatus* Brandegee, Univ. Calif. Publ. Bot. 6: 72. 1914. *Sechiopsis laciniata*

Figure 1: Isotype of *Pterosicyos laciniatus* Brandegee (NY00172502, © Herbarium of New York Botanical Garden)

Figure 2: Isotype of *Parasicyos dieterleae* Lira & R.Torres (BM000884554, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 3: Isotype of *Parasicyos dieterleae* Lira & R.Torres (TEX00208196, © University of Texas at Austin)

(Brandege) Kearns, Syst. Bot. 17(3): 402. 1992. *Sicyos laciniatus* (Brandege) R.Kr.Singh, J. Biodivers. Conservation 9(2): 150. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* L., Sp. Pl. [Linnaeus] 2: 1013. 1753.

Holotype: Mexico, Chiapas, Cerro del Boqueron, September 1913, C.A. Purpus 6915 (UC172957!); isotypes F0055071F!, GH00031929!, NY00172502! (Figure 1), US00036713!.

Distribution: Guatemala (Quetzaltenango, San Marcos and Suchitupéquez) and Mexico (Chiapas).

Etymology: Named after Townshend Stith Brandege (1843–1925), American Botanist.

Sicyos sangeetae R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Parasicyos dieterleae* Lira & R.Torres, Acta Bot. Mex. 16: 98. 1991. *Sicyos dieterleae* (Lira & R.Torres) R.Kr.Singh, J. Biodivers. Conservation 9(2): 139. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* Rodr.-Arév. & Lira, Acta Bot. Mex. 48: 15. 1999.

Holotype: Mexico, Oaxaca, Municipality Teposcolula, Teposcolula district, Cerro El Peñasco al S de Teposcolula, 2200–2550 m, 9 September 1988, R. Torres & M.L. Torres 12318 (MEXU); isotypes BM000884554! (Figure 2), IEB000156490!, TEX00208196! (Figure 3), UCAM011274!.

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Chiapas and Oaxaca).

Etymology: Named after my wife Sangeeta Singh, whose unwavering support and encouragement have been vital to the progression of my botanical research.

Acknowledgements

The author is thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities. I am also grateful to the curators of BM, F, GH, IEB, NY, TEX, UC, UCAM and US for the images and information of type specimens.

References

- Schaefer, H. and Renner, S.S. (2011). Phylogenetic relationships in the order Cucurbitales and a new classification of the gourd family (Cucurbitaceae). *Taxon* 60(1): 122–138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tax.601011>
- Sebastian, P., Schaefer, H., Lira, R., Telford, I.R.H. and Renner, S.S. (2012). Radiation following long-distance dispersal: the contributions of time, opportunity and diaspore morphology in *Sicyos* (Cucurbitaceae). *Journal of Biogeography* 39(8): 1427–1438. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2012.02695.x>
- Singh, R.K. (2025). New combinations in Cucurbitaceae. *Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation* 9(2): 137–152. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15593359>
- Telford, I.R.H., Sebastian, P., Lange, P.J. de, Bruhl, J.J. and Renner, S.S. (2012). Morphological and molecular data reveal three rather than one species of *Sicyos* (Cucurbitaceae) in Australia,

New Zealand and Islands of the South West Pacific. *Australian Systematic Botany* 25(3) 188–201. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SB11032>

Turland, N.J., Wiersema, J.H., Barrie, F.R., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D.L., Herendeen, P.S., Knapp, S., Kusber, W.-H., Li, D.-Z., Marhold, K., May, T.W., McNeill, J., Monro, A.M., Prado, J., Price, M.J. and Smith, G.F. (2018). *International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code)*. *Regnum Vegetabile* 159. Koeltz Botanical Books, Glashütten. <https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>